

Clientelism and infrastructural gaps in Southern Europe: The implications on housing and urban governance

Andreas Panagidis, Effrosyni Roussou

Department of Architecture, University of Cyprus, Cyprus

Keywords: clientelism, southern Europe, infrastructure, participation

1. Introduction

Unaffordable and unsustainable housing is widely regarded as a harsh side-effect of the failure of pro-market policies. The issue is often used to articulate the flaws of dominant responses through political-economic ties that tend to reconstruct new cases of dispossession (Dikeç, 2007). When exploring the ongoing housing crisis, the dominant narratives of urgent fixes to the problem enabled governments face when enacting policy without questioning the insecure foundations of uneven spatial development (Heslop & Ormerod, 2020).

The inability of the state to protect disenfranchised groups, and the deficiencies of public-private neoliberal models of urban governance have contributed to rising levels of distrust in governance institutions. Adding to the widely regarded problem of the global affordable housing gap (Reid, 2023), the infrastructural gap in the Mediterranean region is identified by the deficits (gaps) in the infrastructures required to mitigate overlapping challenges of sustainable development in general (Dalakoglou, 2016). Moreover, the growing role of the private sector in urban governance and public-private alliances, promoting urban entrepreneurialism (Phelps & Miao, 2020), provide private actors with speculative interests greater degrees of influence in the development of urban infrastructure than society as a whole. A continuation of neoliberal urban planning places real barriers to meaningful citizen participation in the development of sustainable cities.

Clientelism and infrastructural gaps

According to Ferrera (1996), Southern European (SE) states have historically shared common traits in terms of governance, including high levels of corporatism in local, regional and national finance management, an elevated degree of collusive relations between public and private actors, and persisting clientelism. Such state-market interactions are observed across SE countries, such as Italy and Greece, to an extent that some scholars describe this phenomenon as the privatisation of politics, whereby developers, hotel owners, ship owners, contractors etc, gain access to political authority (Hadjimichalis, 1998). The tangible failures of the 2008 financial crisis and the more recent refugee crisis, have been strongly felt in conjunction with an ongoing housing crisis (Maloutas et al., 2020) Hence, as the influx of refugees has coincided with a growing housing problem in Europe, the two intersecting crises have made access to housing that is both decent and affordable especially difficult, if not almost impossible, for the most vulnerable groups – namely, refugees and asylum seekers (Paidakaki, 2021).

Recent research is shifting the debate on affordable housing towards a more equitable distribution of resources and a better allocation of funds together with a change in the approach

to housing as another type of social infrastructure, such as schools and hospitals (Lawson et al., 2019). In other words, the proposition to conceptualise affordable housing as essential and guaranteed urban infrastructure is arguably a ground-breaking path to follow, which can contribute to the development of social sustainability (Ponce, 2010; Power & Mee, 2020). Importantly, this research is revealing a number of initiatives ranging from bottom-up and co-produced alternatives to formal processes of urban development, indicating the potential of new state-society relations which are produced through infrastructure (Guarneros-Meza, 2022; Lawhon et al., 2018). Citizen participation in the production of local soft and hard infrastructures is a burgeoning practice of socially-minded urban planning.

In light of the post-crisis outcomes, some governments have begun to shift their approach to incorporate more active citizen participation by encouraging socio-technical innovations, the co-production of resources and new methods of state-society-market collaboration (Fung, 2015; Loeffler & Bovaird, 2017). Dalakoglou (2016) claims that “both state monopoly and public-private partnership paradigms in the governance and development of infrastructures—in the case of Europe at least—are coming to an end as we knew them” (p. 828). However, we argue that in light of a long history of clientelist modes of urban politics and selective pathways of development, the realities on the ground are in fact fraught by society-state contestations and constant struggles by disenfranchised groups to be heard. Moreover, housing as a vital infrastructure for urban life is often missing in these analyses.

What are the implications of such complex relationships on the provision of affordable and sustainable housing as one of the essential infrastructures of cities? Even more, what are the limitations of citizen participation in the design and planning of urban infrastructures, if power imbalances in urban governance coalitions remain? A wider notion of infrastructure, defined as the conditions that provide access to rights and equal urban opportunities and undeniably involves affordable housing, can be considered as realm of state-society interaction which may unlock the potentialities of solutions to a housing crisis.

2. Methods

In this paper we aim to investigate the role of clientelism in urban spatial planning and land development relations, and its impact on citizen participation in local planning. With a broader scope of essential urban infrastructure, from public transportation to affordable housing, we will investigate examples of state-market alliances in Italy, Greece, and Cyprus, which continue to place barriers to citizen participation in the development of sustainable cities. However, as a reaction to these barriers, we also identify community-organised initiatives as opposed to clientelist practices, which are direct actions against the neoliberal, so-called “fixes” to housing and other crises. These actions address different topics including environmental conservation, anti-eviction campaigns, pro-migrant solidarity and anti-corruption demonstrations.

We firstly look specifically into recent examples of clientelist public-private partnerships concerning urban infrastructure and housing in Southern Europe, which are based on unequal power distribution. A cross-comparative reflection of examples of exploitation of power on the one hand and examples of community-based opposition on the other, reveals the antagonistic nature of SE urban governance and planning. Cases of corruption appearing as public scandals in the media are used as opportunities to examine the effects of clientelism and neoliberal policies in South European countries regarding urban development and the lack of credibility of governments in providing infrastructure of care and well-being. Cases of self-organised acts of protest and solidarity, indicate the potential of greater citizen participation in urban development

process in general. However, one must remain critical of the impact of these acts in terms of urban governance and housing policy.

2.1 Case studies

2.1.1 Italy - Organised crime involvement in urban infrastructure

The Mafia Capitale scandal

This scandal involved a network of corruption in Rome, where politicians, bureaucrats, and organised crime figures, such as Massimo Carminati and Salvatore Buzzi, were accused of syphoning off public funds designated for social services such as housing for incoming migrants and refugees, and other welfare-oriented services (DW News, 2017). Commencing in late 2014, when Italian authorities uncovered evidence of corruption and organised crime involvement in the allocation of public contracts and services in Rome, the investigation revealed a web of kickbacks, rigged contracts, public fund embezzlement, and illicit agreements between criminal elements and public officials (Swenson, 2017). The main figures of the scandal, Carminati and Buzzi, were eventually sentenced to 20 and 19 years in jail respectively (Tondo, 2023). The Mafia Capitale scandal highlighted the extensive involvement and influence of organised crime in Italy's local, regional and national political scene.

2.1.2 Greece - Lamda Development land grabs

The Mall of Athens

One of the largest post-2000 real estate scandals in Greece is the case of the Mall of Athens. Lamda Development, one of the most prominent land development corporations in the country, entered into an agreement with the state which revolved around the construction of the "Press Village". The Press Village was designed as a complex of dwellings, an 80-acre park, and a commercial, cultural and entertainment centre that would accommodate approximately 5000 foreign journalists covering the 2004 Olympic Games. Lamda Development was eventually granted access to an additional 43 acres of land adjacent to the "Press Village" site, which belonged to the Worker's Housing Trust¹, and by overriding the initial agreement, aimed at creating a massive commercial and entertainment building (TVXS, 2009, Aretaki, 2013). Since the overall area was zoned as strictly housing, politicians both in the local and national government were involved in passing constitutional and planning regulation amendments to facilitate and fast-track the construction, while Lamda Development failed to meet any of the clauses of the initial agreement. On 27/01/2020 regulations were amended once more to render what used to be South-Eastern Europe's largest illegal structure legal (The Press Project, 2020).

¹ Worker's Housing Trust (Οργανισμός Εργατικής Κατοικίας - ΟΕΚ) was a public agency active between 1954-2012 and tasked with providing affordable housing to lower income households. ΟΕΚ was eventually shut down in 2012, as dictated by the EU Economic Adjustment Programme for Greece.

The Ellinikon project

Another massive Lamda Development endeavour is the Ellinikon urban regeneration project. Currently branded as the largest urban regeneration project in Europe, Ellinikon is a 6800 acre area in southern Attica, and the site where “a cutting-edge urban haven” is set to be created, consisting of “a world-class Metropolitan Park” (The Ellinikon, n.d.), “the upgrade of the Coastal Front” and the creation of “residential developments, hotels, shopping centres, family entertainment venues, museums, cultural venues, health and wellness centers” among others (Lamda Development, n.d.). Lamda Development has secured land use and development rights of the area at a price 5 times lower than its actual value (according to estimations provided by the Technical Chamber of Greece), while no precise prerequisites and obligations were pinpointed to frame the exact nature of this development (The Press Project, 2021). Much of the criticism frames this project as one of the largest public land grab cases, and focuses on the exclusionary nature of the development, which, by outrightly targeting the most affluent members of the international society, may create a ghettoed community in one of Attica’s most prestigious locations (Efimerida ton Sidakton, 2021).

2.1.3 Cyprus – unhinged urbanisation

Residential development in Nicosia’s periphery

Since the 2008 financial crisis and the accompanying demise of Nicosia’s urban centre, around the same time, the Mall of Cyprus was constructed and speculative outward residential development in Nicosia has grown. Details were collected from a personal interview with Ms Agni Petridou, City Engineer of Nicosia Municipality (A. Petridou, personal communication, May, 2015). Overall, from Ms Petridou’s point of view, there has been a lack of enforcement of planning regulations and over-investment in areas such as Latsia, away from the centre. The most important factors have been the prioritisation of building roads in the suburbs and the expansion of residential zones which increase the profitability of land developers but increase public infrastructure costs and make public transportation even more inefficient. Petridou also shared information regarding the connection of private interests such as the actors involved in the development of the Mall and the granting of special favours by the planning department as the planning permission which was granted to the Mall of Cyprus was by derogation (κατα παρέκκλιση).

Cyfield’s monopoly business in state infrastructure projects

The most significant infrastructure in Cyprus has been constructed by Cyfield Group. Between 2015 and 2022, Cyfield was awarded 12% of the total value of all nationally procured tenders (personal analysis of statistical data provided by the Treasury Department). This includes roadworks, sewage infrastructure (including the scandal of bribing the Paphos mayor), luxury residence-high rise buildings, schools, mall, new museum, hospital, football stadium, a new power station. A recent scandal regarding failure to adhere to environmental protection measures during the construction of new roads, has led to a halt of works in Akamas, the island’s most protected natural habitat, due to public outrage regarding the violations.

Perhaps the most publicised scandal has been the case of Cyfield bribing the mayor of Paphos, the island’s westernmost city, with millions of euros in the Paphos Sewerage Board new infrastructure works. Eight years after the case, the company continues to operate with impunity. The president of the Parliamentary Committee on Institutions and Values stated: “This is what the citizens see, this is what society sees, and this is what discredits us and entrenches a feeling of deepest complicity and corruption” (Savva, 2024). These remarks indicate that corruption in the eyes of society leads to diminishing respect and trust in public institutions.

3. Results and discussion

The commonalities of these cases are the institutional environments and regimes which define the ways in which networks of urban development and political actors collaborate. According to Savini and Bertolini (2019), institutions are defined “both as concrete spatial conditions and as immaterial rules and norms, [which] provide the principles by which selections are made in cities [...] for example, institutions are deeply influencing the workings of the housing market, through established regulations and economic rules” (p. 834). These processes are shaped by actors who are either conforming to, or attempting to transform, their institutional environments, policies and planning approaches and are therefore intrinsically political. The actors who are most powerful in urban planning institutions, are those whose judgement and ability is prioritised and even uncontested when the trajectories of new urban developments are being decided.

These obvious instances of corruption arguably intensify an already precarious bond of (mis)trust in, and a diminished level of respect for public institutions. This conflictual relation between governing bodies and the various facets of society may lead to an apolitical approach to urban development - meaning, a less-than-democratic system of governance and planning with direct implications in the sustainability and affordability of cities. Hence, the attempts by Southern states to incorporate EU sustainable development goals in their housing agendas at the city/local level, or, more specifically, implement participatory approaches e.g. in neighbourhood planning, are sometimes received with scepticism by the groups that have been side-lined in the past.

While new instances of corruption and clientelism are arguably continuing to emerge, SE states present a long history of bottom-up tactics, opposing dominant spatial/planning strategies. Tactics, rather than formal strategies, are niches of improvisation and experimentation that rely on a day-to-day responsiveness to shifting conditions, and a steady support of organising teams and communities with a sense of social capital. These tactics pose as reactions to the exclusionary urbanism in line with neoliberal development regimes. Anti-eviction movements, housing squats, neighbourhood social spaces are but a few examples of side-lined groups attempting to create prefigurative socio-spatial instances and housing configurations in the city that resist the various hegemonic planning and development agendas (Franks, 2003).

However, meaningful as these tactics may be in reproducing social capital, their impact on housing policy is often limited. Occasionally, national/local governments may attempt to suppress such tactics by associating the exhibited disruptiveness with a projected negative impact on the urban landscape. This negative impact may, therefore, be spotlighted in public discussions to draw the general public's focus away from other important topics and toward the groups using these tactics. The inherent precarity that characterises the latter, paired with the unwillingness of local and national governments to examine, negotiate and discuss the diverse visions co-existing in SE cities, contribute to the conflictual relation between institutions and citizens, thus perpetuating the cycle of mistrust. Finally, the obstinance of state planning and housing departments which cannot deviate from their established ways and hierarchical organisation pose serious questions regarding the accessibility provided to local actors and especially minority groups.

4. Conclusion

Clientelist and corrupt relations in local economic development decision-making are beginning to reveal a regional commonality between SE countries with regard to the barriers to citizen participation in urban development. More specifically, what these case studies have in common is the disenfranchisement of less-powerful groups, even more so minorities, who lack the political influence and financial capacity to claim the right to the neoliberal city. The bottom-up tactics that are occasionally employed by these groups, and their subsequent suppression by governing institutions, present a missed opportunity for dialogue and (some level of) reconciliation.

The expected outcome of this research is a set of reflections on the antagonistic relation between the clientelist state-speculative private actor transactions and the bottom up attempts to claim a seat at the decision-making table of urban infrastructure development. Finally, through the exploration of these opposing practices we aim to critically contextualise citizen participation approaches within the specific limitations of the Southern European socio-political landscape.

Acknowledgment

This paper is an output of A. Panagidis and E. Roussou's doctoral research, conducted under the auspices of RE-DWELL, an Innovative Training Network (ITN) funded by the H2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie programme of the European Union (2020-24), with project number 956082.

References

- Aretaki, M. (2013, April 5). The Mall Athens: Σκάνδαλο όπως και αν το δεις [The Mall Athens: No matter how you look at it, it's a scandal]. The Press Project. <https://thepressproject.gr/the-mall-athens-skandalo-opos-kai-an-to-deis/>
- Dalakoglou, D. (2016). Infrastructural gap: Commons, state and anthropology. *City*, 20(6), 822–831. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13604813.2016.1241524>
- Dikeç, M. (2007). *Badlands of the Republic: Space, Politics and Urban Policy*. Blackwell Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1016/10.1002/9780470712788>
- DW News. (2017, July 20). Mafia Capitale: Rome racket convicted. <https://www.dw.com/en/mafia-capitale-rome-court-convicts-racket-leaders-who-extorted-city-officials/a-39774910>
- Efimerida ton Sidakton. (2021, March 24). Τρία σκάνδαλα σε συσκευασία ενός [Three scandals packaged as one]. https://www.efsyn.gr/politiki/i-apopsi-tis-efsyn/286895_tria-skandala-se-syskeyasia-enos
- Ferrera, M. (1996). The “Southern Model” of Welfare in Social Europe. *Journal of European Social Policy*, 6(1), 17-37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/095892879600600102>
- Fung, A. (2015). Putting the Public Back into Governance: The Challenges of Citizen Participation and Its Future. *Public Administration Review*, 75(4), 513–522. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12361>
- Heslop, J., & Ormerod, E. (2020). The Politics of Crisis: Deconstructing the Dominant Narratives of the Housing Crisis. *Antipode*, 52(1), 145–163. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12585>

- Lamda Development. (n.d.). The Hellinikon. <https://www.lamdadev.com/en/investment-portfolio/the-hellinikon.html>
- Lawhon, M., Nilsson, D., Silver, J., Ernstson, H., & Lwasa, S. (2018). Thinking through heterogeneous infrastructure configurations. *Urban Studies*, 55(4), 720–732. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098017720149>
- Lawson, J., Denham, T., Dodson, J., Flanagan, K., Jacobs, K., Martin, C., Van Den Nouwelant, R., Pawson, H., & Troy, L. (2019). Social housing as infrastructure: Rationale, prioritisation and investment pathway. In *AHURI Final Report* (Issue 315). <https://doi.org/10.18408/ahuri-5314001>
- Lemanski, C. (2020). Viewpoint infrastructural citizenship: (de)constructing state-society relations. *International Development Planning Review*, 42(2), 115–125. <https://doi.org/10.3828/idpr.2019.39>
- Loeffler, E., & Bovaird, T. (2017). From Participation to Co-production: Widening and Deepening the Contributions of Citizens to Public Services and Outcomes. In E. Ongaro, S. Van Thiel (Eds.), *The Palgrave Handbook of Public Administration and Management in Europe*, 403–423. https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-55269-3_21
- Maloutas, T., Siatitsa, D., Balampanidis, D. (2020). Access to Housing and Social Inclusion in a Post-Crisis Era: Contextualizing Recent Trends in the City of Athens. *Social Inclusion*, 8(3), 5–15. <https://doi.org/10.17645/si.v8i3.2778>
- Paidakaki, A. (2021). Social Innovation in the Times of a European Twofold Refugee-Housing Crisis. Evidence from the Homelessness Sector. *European Journal of Homelessness*, 15(1), 24.
- Phelps, N. A., & Miao, J. T. (2020). Varieties of urban entrepreneurialism. *Dialogues in Human Geography*, 10(3), 304–321. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2043820619890438>
- Ponce, J. (2010). Affordable housing as urban infrastructure: A comparative study from a European perspective. *The Urban Lawyer*, 42(4), 223–245.
- Power, E. R., & Mee, K. J. (2020). Housing: an infrastructure of care. *Housing Studies*, 35(3), 484–505. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2019.1612038>
- Reid, A. (2023). Closing the Affordable Housing Gap: Identifying the Barriers Hindering the Sustainable Design and Construction of Affordable Homes. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15118754>
- Savini, F., & Bertolini, L. (2019). Urban experimentation as a politics of niches. *Environment and Planning A*, 51(4), 831–848. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308518X19826085>
- Savva, G. (2014, February 14). Ατιμώρητες εταιρείες που βάσει απόφασης Δικαστηρίου είχαν εμπλοκή στην υπόθεση ΣΑΠΑ, λέχθηκε στην Επ. Θεσμών. CNA. <https://www.cna.org.cy/article/6231885/atimorites-etaireies-poy-vasei-apofasis-dikastiriou-eichan-ebloki-stin-ypothesi-sapa-lechthike-stin-ep-thesmon>
- Swenson, K. (2017, July 21). The last king of Rome: How a one-eyed gangster conned the Italian capital into a debt crisis. *The Washington Post*. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/morning-mix/wp/2017/07/21/the-last-king-of-rome-how-a-one-eyed-gangster-conned-the-italian-capital-into-a-debt-crisis/>
- The Ellinikon. (n.d.). <https://theellinikon.com.gr/en/about-us/the-ellinikon/>

- The Press Project. (2020, February 2). Με τη σφραγίδα του ΣτΕ νομιμο το μέχρι πρότινος αυθαίρετο “The Mall Athens” [By order from the national assembly The Mall Athens gains legal status]. <https://thepressproject.gr/me-ti-sfragida-tou-ste-nomimo-to-mechri-protinis-afthereto-the-mall-athens/>
- The Press Project. (2021, June 29). “Υφαρπαγή δημόσιας περιουσίας” και “παράδοση του Ελληνικού χωρίς προϋποθέσεις στη Lamda” [“Embezzlement of public property” and “Unconditional delivery of Ellinikon to Lamda”]. <https://thepressproject.gr/yfarpagi-dimosias-periousias-kai-paradosi-tou-ellinikou-choris-proypotheseis-sti-lamda/>
- Tondo, L. (2023, November 20). More than 200 mobsters convicted in Italian mafia maxi-trial. The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2023/nov/20/more-than-200-mobsters-convicted-in-italian-mafia-maxi-trial>
- TVXS. (2009, May 7). Mall: "Το μεγαλύτερο αυθαίρετο της Ευρώπης" [Mall: "The largest illegal structure in Europe"]. <https://tvxs.gr/news/ellada/mall-to-megalytero-aythaireto-tis-eyropis/>